

THE APPRENTICESHIP ADVENTURE WITH 2GO TRAVEL: ITS CONTRIBUTION TO THE LEARNING EXPERIENCES AND PROFESSIONAL GROWTH OF TOURISM STUDENTS

Lean F. Villanobos, Maria Mae D. Elumbra,
Kathleen Claire P. Jamera, Daniell F. Kitane

*Metro Dumaguete College, Dumaguete City
Negros Oriental, Philippines*

ABSTRACT

Apprenticeship programs play a crucial role in bridging theoretical learning and industry exposure. The apprenticeship experience with 2GO Travel provides students with real-world opportunities that enhance their learning experiences and professional development. This study aimed to determine the contribution of the apprenticeship program with 2GO Travel to the learning experiences and professional growth of tourism students. A descriptive -correlational research design was employed using a validated survey questionnaire administered to 37 tourism students from two higher education institutions in Dumaguete City who participated in the apprenticeship program. The statistical tools used were the weighted mean and Pearson's correlation coefficient. The results revealed that the apprenticeship program made a very high contribution to students' learning experiences and professional growth. Specifically, it enhanced their application of academic knowledge, technical and practical skills, communication and customer service abilities, and professional values. Furthermore, the program improved students' industry exposure, problem-solving skills, teamwork, and career readiness. A significant relationship between learning experiences and professional growth was also found. The study concludes that the 2GO Travel apprenticeship program is an effective means of preparing tourism students for the demands of the industry. It highlights the importance of integrating a well-planned apprenticeship program into tourism education to develop competent, confident, and industry-ready graduates.

Keywords: *Apprenticeship, Experiential Learning, Tourism Students, Professional Growth, Learning Experiences, Career Readiness*

INTRODUCTION

The global tourism and hospitality industry continues to face significant challenges in preparing graduates who can effectively meet the evolving demands of the workplace. Rapid technological advancement, changing customer expectations, globalization, and the long-term effects of the COVID-19 pandemic have transformed the skills and competencies required in the tourism sector. As a result, many higher education institutions struggle to bridge the gap between theoretical instruction and practical industry application. In response to these concerns, apprenticeship programs and work-integrated learning (WIL) have become increasingly important in developing industry-ready graduates through experiential learning opportunities. According to Xu et al. (2022), structured WIL experiences improve students' reflective learning, practical skill application, and readiness for real-world work environments. Likewise, Pianda et al. (2024) emphasized that internship experiences significantly influence students' employability and professional identity development across various countries. Furthermore, Safri et al. (2026) found that WIL-based internships enhance customer service, communication, and problem-solving skills, which are essential competencies in the tourism and hospitality industry. Despite these initiatives, concerns regarding graduate preparedness and the effectiveness of experiential learning programs remain evident worldwide.

In the Philippine, tourism and hospitality programs continue to recognize experiential learning as a vital component of quality education; however, challenges still exist in ensuring that apprenticeship programs effectively contribute to students' professional growth and industry readiness. Several studies have emphasized the importance of internships and industry immersion in improving students' technical competencies and employability. Devota (2025) revealed that shipboard apprenticeships enable maritime students to connect theoretical learning with actual vessel operations, thereby strengthening adaptability and problem-solving skills. Similarly, Baluyut (2025) highlighted that strong industry partnerships are necessary to bridge the gap between classroom instruction and workplace expectations in tourism and hospitality education. Garcia (2025) further stressed that community-based and experiential learning initiatives improve students' professionalism and workplace preparedness, while Galon (2025) found that internship experiences help tourism students develop communication skills, confidence, and adaptability. Although these studies confirm the value of experiential learning, limited research has specifically examined the contribution of apprenticeship programs offered by major tourism transport providers such as 2GO Travel to tourism students' learning experiences and professional development.

Previous studies primarily focused on general internship experiences, employability, and industry immersion in tourism and hospitality education. However, there remains a lack of localized research examining how specific apprenticeship programs contribute to both the learning experiences and professional growth of tourism

students. In particular, limited studies have explored the apprenticeship experiences of tourism students engaged in shipboard and travel-related operations under 2GO Travel. Existing literature also provides insufficient evidence regarding how such apprenticeship programs influence students' technical skills, customer service competencies, workplace confidence, teamwork, and career readiness. This gap in the literature highlights the need for further investigation into the effectiveness of apprenticeship programs in enhancing students' preparedness for the tourism industry.

Thus, this study was conducted to determine the contribution of the 2GO Travel apprenticeship program to the learning experiences and professional growth of tourism students. Specifically, the study aimed to evaluate how the apprenticeship enhanced students' academic knowledge, technical and practical skills, communication abilities, industry exposure, and career readiness. The findings of this study may provide valuable insights for educational institutions such as Metro Dumaguete College and Foundation University, as well as industry partners, in improving apprenticeship design, strengthening curriculum integration, and enhancing experiential learning strategies. Ultimately, the study seeks to contribute to the development of competent, confident, and industry-ready tourism professionals in the Philippines.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the contribution of the Apprenticeship Adventure with 2GO Travel to the learning experiences and professional growth of Tourism students.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. To what extent has the apprenticeship with 2GO Travel contributed to the learning experiences of students in terms of:
 - 1.1 application of academic knowledge;
 - 1.2 technical and practical skills;
 - 1.3 enhancement of communication and customer service skills;
 - 1.4 strengthening of professional values and work ethics?
2. What is the extent of contribution of the 2GO Travel Apprenticeship to students professional growth in terms of:
 - 2.1 industry exposure and workplace adaptation;
 - 2.2 problem-solving and critical thinking abilities;
 - 2.3 teamwork and collaboration;
 - 2.4 career readiness and confidence building?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of the 2GO Travel apprenticeship's contribution to students' learning experiences and professional growth after the 2GO travel apprenticeship?

METHODOLOGY

Research design

The study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design to examine the learning experiences and professional growth of tourism students during their apprenticeship with 2GO Travel. The study was descriptive in nature because it aimed to present a clear and systematic account of the learning experiences and professional growth of tourism students during their apprenticeship. It focused on describing how students perceived the contribution of the apprenticeship in terms of the application of academic knowledge, development of technical and practical skills, enhancement of communication and customer service skills, and strengthening of professional values and work ethics.

On the other hand, the study was correlational because it examined the relationship between two main variables: students' learning experiences and their professional growth. Specifically, it determined whether a significant relationship existed between these variables following the apprenticeship experience. This approach also allowed for the analysis of how key factors such as the application of academic knowledge, technical and practical skills development, communication and customer service skills, and professional values influenced students' overall professional growth.

Research respondents

The respondents of the study were the Tourism students enrolled in the Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management program at Metro Dumaguete College and Foundation University who have completed the apprenticeship program with 2GO Travel. Purposive sampling was utilized to select the respondents, ensuring that only students with firsthand experience of the apprenticeship was included. A total of 37 Tourism students was chosen as respondents.

The selection of respondents aimed to obtain insights into their learning experiences and professional growth following their completed apprenticeship. Data were collected from students who had already participated in the program, allowing the study to gather relevant and meaningful information on how the apprenticeship influenced their academic knowledge, technical skills, professional values, and career readiness. Below is the distribution of the respondents.

Institution	Number of Respondents
MDC (Metro Dumaguete College)	27
FU (Foundation University)	10
Total	37

Research instruments

In gathering the necessary data for the study, the researchers utilized a validated researcher-made survey questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed to collect data on tourism students' learning experiences and professional growth during their completed apprenticeship with 2GO Travel.

The first part of the questionnaire contained a disclosure statement, followed by a brief letter introducing the purpose of the study and outlining its objectives. Clear instructions were provided to ensure that the respondents fully understood the content and were able to accomplish the survey accurately and independently.

To ensure the validity of the instrument, the researchers consulted their subject teacher and three experts in the field of tourism and hospitality management. The content of the questionnaire was reviewed to confirm that the indicators were coherent, relevant, and appropriate for the objectives of the study. Suggestions and corrections from the experts were carefully considered, and necessary modifications were made to improve the quality and validity of the instrument.

In assessing the reliability of the instrument, a dry run was conducted. Ten respondents were selected for this purpose, and the items were evaluated using Cronbach's alpha test to measure internal consistency. The results of the dry run indicated that the indicators in each statement of the problem demonstrated acceptable levels of reliability and consistency.

Indicators	Cronbach's Alpha Value
1.1 application of academic knowledge	a = 0.87
1.2 development of technical and practical skills	a = 0.86
1.3 enhancement of communication and customer service skills	a = 0.91
1.4 strengthening of professional values and work ethics	a = 0.85
2.1 industry exposure and workplace adaptation	a = 0.72
2.2 problem-solving and critical thinking abilities	a = 0.87
2.3 teamwork and collaboration	a = 0.82
2.4 career readiness and confidence building	a = 0.92

These results suggested that the instrument is reliable and suitable for the use in the actual data gathering process. This process was to ensure that the survey questionnaire is both valid and reliable for the study.

RESULTS

Table 1.1
Extent of the Apprenticeship with 2GO Travel contributed to the Learning Experiences of Students in terms of Application of Academic Knowledge

Academic Knowledge	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Contribution
<i>My apprenticeship with 2GO Travel has...</i>			
1. given me the chance to practice the tourism concepts I learned in my classes.	4.59	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. allowed me to use classroom knowledge in handling actual tasks on board.	4.51	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. helped me realize how my academic lessons apply in real customer service situations.	4.49	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. provided me with opportunities to connect theories from school to real work experiences.	4.46	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. made me more confident in applying what I studied to real workplace challenges.	4.62	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	4.54	Strongly Agree	Very High
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Contribution	
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High	
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate	
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low	
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	

Table 1.1 shows the extent to which the apprenticeship with 2GO Travel contributed to the learning experiences of students in terms of Application of Academic Knowledge. The findings reveal that the apprenticeship enhances students' ability to apply academic knowledge, with an overall weighted mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.54$), indicating "Very High" perceived extent of contribution. This suggests that students highly valued the opportunity to bridge classroom theory with real-world tourism practice. The findings show that the overall composite mean for the application of academic knowledge is ($w\bar{x} = 4.54$), indicating a very high level of perceived contribution from the apprenticeship.

Table 1.2
Extent of the Apprenticeship with 2GO Travel contributed to the Learning Experiences of Students in terms of Development on Technical and Practical Skills

Development on Technical and Practical Skills	$\bar{w}\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Contribution
My apprenticeship with 2GO Travel has...			
1. improved my ability to handle tourism-related tools, systems, or procedures.	4.43	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. taught me practical techniques that cannot be learned only in the classroom.	4.59	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. developed my skills in dealing with real-life service operations.	4.65	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. enhanced my problem-handling skills in actual work scenarios.	4.59	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. given me hands-on experience that strengthened my technical knowledge.	4.68	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	4.59	Strongly Agree	Very High
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Contribution	
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High	
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate	
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low	
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	

Table 1.2 displays the extent to which the apprenticeship with 2GO Travel contributed to the learning experiences of students in terms of Development of Technical and Practical Skills. The findings reveal that the apprenticeship significantly enhanced students’ technical and practical competencies, with a composite mean of ($\bar{w}\bar{x} = 4.59$), indicating a very high extent of contribution.

Table 1.3
Extent of the Apprenticeship with 2GO Travel contributed to the Learning Experiences of Students in terms of Enhancement of Communication and Customer Service Skills

Enhancement of Communication and Customer Service Skills	$\bar{w}\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Contribution
My apprenticeship with 2GO Travel has...			
1. improved my ability to communicate clearly with the passengers and staff.	4.62	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. trained me to handle customer inquiries and complaints more effectively.	4.68	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. taught me how to adjust my communication style depending on the situation.	4.54	Strongly Agree	Very High

4. enhanced my confidence in providing professional customer service.	4.62	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. helped me practice active listening and empathy when assisting clients.	4.70	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	4.63	Strongly Agree	Very High
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Contribution	
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High	
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate	
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low	
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	

Table 1.3 describes the extent to which the apprenticeship with 2GO Travel contributed to the learning experiences of students in terms of Enhancement of Communication and Customer Service Skills. The findings reveal that the apprenticeship played important role in improving students' communication abilities and customer service competencies, with a composite mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.63$), indicating a very high extent of contribution.

Table 1.4
Extent of the Apprenticeship with 2GO Travel contributed to the Learning Experiences of Students in terms of Strengthening of Professional Values and Work Ethics

Strengthening of Professional Values and Work Ethics	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Contribution
<i>My apprenticeship with 2GO Travel has...</i>			
1. instilled in me the importance of punctuality and responsibility at work.	4.62	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. taught me how to maintain professionalism in workplace situations.	4.62	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. developed my sense of discipline in following rules and standards.	4.70	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. encouraged me to demonstrate integrity and honesty in my tasks.	4.70	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. strengthened my appreciation for teamwork and respect for colleagues.	4.65	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	4.66	Strongly Agree	Very High
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Contribution	
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High	
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate	
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low	
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	

Table 1.4 demonstrates the extent to which the apprenticeship with 2GO Travel contributed to the learning experiences of students in terms of strengthening professional values and work ethics. The findings show that professional values and work ethics have a composite mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.66$), indicating a “Very High Contribution” on students’ learning and workplace preparedness.

Table 2.1
Extent of Contribution of the 2GO Travel Apprenticeship to Students’ Professional Growth in terms of Industry Exposure and Workplace Adaptation

Industry Exposure and Workplace Adaptation	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Contribution
<i>My apprenticeship with 2GO Travel has...</i>			
1. exposed me to the real-world environment of the tourism and hospitality industry.	4.70	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. allowed me to observe and adapt to workplace culture and practice.	4.70	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. helped me adjust to different work schedules and responsibilities.	4.65	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. given me insights into how professionals handle tourism operations.	4.57	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. taught me how to quickly adapt to changes and challenges in the workplace.	4.54	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	4.63	Strongly Agree	Very High
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Contribution	
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High	
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate	
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low	
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	

Table 2.1 illustrates the extent of contribution of the 2GO Travel apprenticeship to students’ professional growth in terms of industry exposure and workplace adaptation. The findings indicate that the apprenticeship program has a composite mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.63$), reflecting a “Very High” perceived extent of contribution to students’ professional competencies.

Table 2.2
Extent of Contribution of the 2GO Travel Apprenticeship to Students' Professional Growth in terms of Problem-Solving and Critical Thinking Abilities

Problem-Solving and Critical Thinking Abilities	$\bar{w}x$	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Contribution
My apprenticeship with 2GO Travel has...			
1. trained me to think critically when unexpected problems arise.	4.54	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. improved my ability to analyze and evaluate different work situations.	4.46	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. taught me to create practical solutions in customer-related issues.	4.49	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. enhanced my decision-making skills under pressure.	4.54	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. developed my confidence in handling real problems with limited supervision.	4.57	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	4.52	Strongly Agree	Very High
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Contribution	
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High	
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate	
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low	
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	

Table 2.2 presents the extent of contribution of the 2GO Travel apprenticeship to students' professional growth in terms of problem-solving and critical thinking abilities. The findings show that the apprenticeship program has a "Very High" ($\bar{w}x = 4.52$) perceived extent of contribution to students' cognitive and analytical skills.

Table 2.3
Extent of Contribution of the 2GO Travel Apprenticeship to Students' Professional Growth in terms of Teamwork and Collaboration

Teamwork and Collaboration	$\bar{w}x$	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Contribution
My apprenticeship with 2GO Travel has...			
1. taught me the importance of working well with colleagues.	4.51	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. developed my cooperation skills in group tasks and projects.	4.57	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. gave me opportunities to contribute ideas with others, including different opinions and work styles.	4.54	Strongly Agree	Very High

4. helped me learn how to respect and value the contributions of others.	4.59	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. improved my ability to collaborate with people from diverse backgrounds.	4.54	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	4.55	Strongly Agree	Very High

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Contribution
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 2.3 reveals the extent to which the 2GO Travel Apprenticeship contributed to students’ professional growth in terms of Teamwork and Collaboration. The findings indicate that the apprenticeship program has a composite mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.55$), reflecting a “Very High” perceived extent of contribution to students’ teamwork and collaboration skills.

Table 2.4
Extent of Contribution of the 2GO Travel Apprenticeship to Students’ Professional Growth in terms of Career Readiness and Confidence Building

Career Readiness and Confidence Building	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Contribution
<i>My apprenticeship with 2GO Travel has...</i>			
1. made me more prepared for future career opportunities.	4.49	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. boosted my confidence in handling tasks during my apprenticeship.	4.57	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. given me a clearer idea of my strengths and weaknesses as a future professional.	4.57	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. encouraged me to pursue further learning and growth in the industry.	4.62	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. inspired me to set career goals and work hard to achieve them.	4.57	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	4.56	Strongly Agree	Very High
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Contribution	
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High	
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate	
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low	
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	

Table 2.4 indicates the extent of contribution of the 2GO Travel apprenticeship to students’ professional growth in terms of Career Readiness and Confidence Building. The

findings show that the apprenticeship program has a composite mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.56$), indicating a “Very High” perceived extent of contribution to students’ career readiness and professional confidence.

Table 3
Significant Relationship between the Extent of the Apprenticeship’s Contribution to Students’ Learning Experiences and Professional Growth during the 2GO Travel Apprenticeship

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Application of Academic Knowledge				
Industry Exposure and Workplace Adaptation	0.729	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Problem-Solving and Critical Thinking Abilities	0.723	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Teamwork and Collaboration	0.642	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Career Readiness and Confidence Building	0.737	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Development on Technical and Practical Skills				
Industry Exposure and Workplace Adaptation	0.824	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Problem-Solving and Critical Thinking Abilities	0.812	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Teamwork and Collaboration	0.822	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Career Readiness and Confidence Building	0.905	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Enhancement of Communication and Customer Service Skills				
Industry Exposure and Workplace Adaptation	0.811	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Problem-Solving and Critical Thinking Abilities	0.837	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Teamwork and Collaboration	0.839	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Career Readiness and Confidence Building	0.918	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Strengthening of Professional Values and Work Ethics				
Industry Exposure and Workplace Adaptation	0.830	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Problem-Solving and Critical Thinking Abilities	0.741	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Teamwork and Collaboration	0.845	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant

Career Readiness and Confidence Building	0.821	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
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Table 3 exposes the relationship between the extent of the 2GO Travel Apprenticeship’s contribution to students’ learning experiences and professional growth, and the extent to which various factors influence students’ development in application of academic knowledge, technical and practical skills, communication and customer service skills, and professional values and work ethics. Using Pearson’s Correlation Coefficient, it reveals that all p-values are less than the level of significance (0.05). These figures warrant the rejection of the null hypothesis, indicating that there is a significant relationship between the extent of apprenticeship contributions and students’ perceived development across all measured learning and professional growth dimensions.

DISCUSSION

Extent of the Apprenticeship with 2GO Travel contributed to the Learning Experiences of Students

1.1 Application of Academic Knowledge

Table 1.1 shows that the apprenticeship enhances students’ ability to apply academic knowledge, with an overall weighted mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.54$), indicating "Very High" perceived extent of contribution. Among the indicators, the highest mean was ($w\bar{x} = 4.62$), which reflects that students strongly agreed that the apprenticeship made them more confident in applying what they learned to real workplace challenges. Followed by "given me the chance to practice the tourism concepts I learned in my classes" ($w\bar{x} = 4.59$), "allowed me to use classroom knowledge in handling actual tasks on board" ($w\bar{x} = 4.51$), "helped me realize how my academic lessons apply in real customer service situations" ($w\bar{x} = 4.49$) and "provided me with opportunities to connect theories from school to real work experiences" ($w\bar{x} = 4.46$). This indicates that direct engagement with operational tasks allowed students to contextualize theoretical concepts effectively.

A compelling explanation for these findings is the recognized value of experiential learning in tourism education. According to González-Herrera and Escobar (2021), experiential learning opportunities, such as fieldwork or internships, improve students’ ability to apply academic knowledge in real-world contexts. The apprenticeship with 2GO Travel aligns with this by providing structured exposure to actual tourism operations, allowing students to practice and test classroom concepts.

Moreover, the strong impact of applying academic knowledge is supported by Croft and Wang (2023), who emphasized that experiential learning fosters meaningful connections between theoretical understanding and practical execution, reinforcing students’ competence and readiness for the industry. Moreover, Hyasat (2022), also highlighted that internships enable students to translate classroom lessons into professional tasks, which enhances both skill application and critical reflection.

Additionally, Garcia (2025), found that bridging theory with practice builds confidence and professional preparedness, echoing the high ratings observed in this study.

1.2 Technical and Practical Skills

Table 1.2 revealed that the apprenticeship significantly enhanced students' technical and practical competencies, with a composite mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.59$), indicating a very high extent of contribution. Among the indicators, the highest mean is ($w\bar{x} = 4.68$), which shows that students strongly agreed that the apprenticeship provided hands-on experience that strengthened their technical knowledge. Followed by "developed my skills in dealing with real-life service operations" ($w\bar{x} = 4.65$), "taught me practical techniques that cannot be learned only in the classroom" and "enhanced my problem-handling skills in actual work scenarios" ($w\bar{x} = 4.59$). On the other hand, "improved my ability to handle tourism-related tools, systems, or procedures" ($w\bar{x} = 4.43$) is slightly lower but still very high, indicating that while all skill development aspects were impactful, hands-on exposure and complex operational tasks were perceived as more influential in enhancing overall competency. This suggests that students highly valued the hands-on exposure provided by the apprenticeship, which allowed them to strengthen skills that are difficult to acquire in the classroom alone.

These findings is supported by the study of Tavitiyaman, et al. (2023), that internship experiences provide tourism students with critical opportunities to develop technical and operational skills that are difficult to teach in traditional classroom settings. The 2GO Travel apprenticeship aligns with this perspective by offering practical tasks and responsibilities that require students to apply classroom knowledge to real-world scenarios.

Moreover, Abd El Hamid et al. (2025), who emphasized that practical training infrastructure and structured programs enhance technical competencies in tourism students. Nguyen et al. (2021), also reported that work-integrated learning experiences improve students' practical abilities and operational readiness, confirming that exposure to authentic industry environments is crucial for skill acquisition. Additionally, Alharethi et al. (2025), found that internships positively influence students' role clarity, technical competence, and work readiness, aligning with the very high ratings observed in this study.

1.3 Enhancement of Communication and Customer Service Skills

Table 1.3 describes the extent to which the apprenticeship with 2GO Travel contributed to the learning experiences of students in terms of Enhancement of Communication and Customer Service Skills. The findings reveal that the apprenticeship played important role in improving students' communication abilities and customer service competencies, with a composite mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.63$), indicating a very high extent of contribution. Among the indicators, the highest mean is ($w\bar{x} = 4.70$), which shows that students strongly agree that the apprenticeship helped them practice active listening and empathy when assisting clients, followed by "trained me to handle customer inquiries and complaints more effectively" ($w\bar{x} = 4.68$), "improved my ability to communicate clearly with

the passengers and staff” and “enhanced my confidence in providing professional customer service” ($w\bar{x} = 4.62$), and “taught me how to adjust my communication style depending on the situation” ($w\bar{x} = 4.54$). These results suggest that the apprenticeship effectively enhanced students’ communication skills and customer service competencies through meaningful real-world exposure.

This aligns with the study of Avleeva et al. (2025), hospitality internships enhance students’ soft skills, particularly communication, empathy, and client engagement, by providing structured opportunities to interact with real customers. This aligns with the high ratings for active listening and empathy observed in this study.

Also, the importance of communication adaptability corresponds with the findings of Tavitiyaman et al. (2023), who emphasized that internships improve students’ ability to adjust communication strategies across different professional contexts, fostering confidence and career readiness. Wanitchanon, et al. (2024), further supported these results, noting that lecturers and employers consistently regard communication and client interaction as critical outcomes of work-integrated learning programs.

The development of professional customer service skills also aligns with Khuadthong, et al. (2025), who found that work-integrated learning strengthens students’ social skills, including empathy, conflict resolution, and effective client communication. These experiences not only enhance students’ immediate performance but also prepare them for long-term professional success in tourism and hospitality industries.

1.4. Strengthening of Professional Values and Work Ethics

Table 1.4 demonstrates the extent to which the apprenticeship with 2GO Travel contributed to the learning experiences of students in terms of strengthening professional values and work ethics. The findings show that professional values and work ethics have a composite mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.66$), indicating a “Very High Contribution” on students’ learning and workplace preparedness. The highest mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.70$) is recorded for the items “developed my sense of discipline in following rules and standards” and “encouraged me to demonstrate integrity and honesty in my tasks,” suggesting that the apprenticeship is particularly effective in cultivating discipline and ethical behavior among students. Followed by “strengthened my appreciation for teamwork and respect for colleagues” ($w\bar{x} = 4.65$), “instilled in me the importance of punctuality” and “responsibility at work and taught me how to maintain professionalism in workplace situations” ($w\bar{x} = 4.62$). This suggests that the apprenticeship instills essential professional values that are highly valued by students and significantly contribute to their development as future tourism professionals.

According to Tian et al. (2025), internship experiences combined with ethics education significantly enhance students’ ethical judgment, discipline, and adherence to workplace standards. The 2GO Travel apprenticeship aligns with this by providing real-world opportunities where students practice responsibility, integrity, and respect. Furthermore, the emphasis on teamwork and professional conduct aligns with the findings

of Lam, et al. (2024), who reported that positive internship characteristics, including guidance and structured tasks, shape students' professional attitudes and job involvement. This underscores that practical, supervised experiences are effective in reinforcing workplace values and behaviors.

The importance of discipline and responsibility is further supported by Andriyatno, et al. (2023), who found that hospitality students' professionalism including punctuality, rule-following, and task responsibility improves significantly through structured internship programs. Similarly, Avleeva, et al. (2025), emphasized that internships strengthen interpersonal competencies and soft skills, such as respect, accountability, and professional conduct, which are integral to work ethics.

Extent of Contribution of the 2GO Travel Apprenticeship to Students' Professional Growth

2.1 Industry Exposure and Workplace Adaptation

Table 2.1 illustrates the extent of contribution of the 2GO Travel apprenticeship to students' professional growth in terms of industry exposure and workplace adaptation. The findings indicate that the apprenticeship program has a composite mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.63$), reflecting a "Very High" perceived extent of contribution to students' professional competencies. The highest mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.70$) is obtained by the items "exposed me to the real-world environment of the tourism and hospitality industry" and "allowed me to observe and adapt to workplace culture and practice," showing that direct industry exposure and cultural immersion are the most impactful aspects of the program. Followed by "helped me adjust to different work schedules and responsibilities" ($w\bar{x} = 4.65$), "given me insights into how professionals handle tourism operations" with a mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.57$). Meanwhile, the lowest mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.54$) is recorded for the item "taught me how to quickly adapt to changes and challenges in the workplace," Although identified as the lowest, these ratings still fall within the "very high extent", indicating consistently high evaluations across all indicators, with only a minimal difference of 0.16 between the highest and lowest means. The very high agreement among respondents indicates that hands-on experience and observation of professional practices are key in preparing students for future careers.

These results align with the study of Alharethi, et al. (2025), internships significantly enhance students' work readiness and their ability to cope with professional demands. The 2GO Travel apprenticeship, by immersing students in real-world operations, aligns with this trend by providing authentic learning experiences that prepare them for professional roles.

In addition, the significance of observing and adapting to workplace culture aligns with the findings of Pantaruk, et al. (2025), who emphasized that experiential learning through internships develops professional competencies, including communication, teamwork, and adaptability, which are essential for employability in the hospitality sector.

The importance of reflective learning during internships is also supported by Ng, et al. (2023), who found that environmental factors and structured guidance in internships positively influence students' career intentions and their professional development. This reinforces the idea that structured exposure and observation in real-world settings are key contributors to the students' learning outcomes in the 2GO Travel apprenticeship.

Furthermore, the role of mentorship and internship satisfaction in shaping career commitment is highlighted by Hu et al. (2025), who argued that supportive internship experiences enhance both skills and long-term engagement in the industry. The strong impact ratings suggest that students highly value the guidance, supervision, and experiential opportunities provided during their apprenticeship, which strengthens their professional growth.

2.2 Problem-Solving and Critical Thinking Abilities

Table 2.2 presents the extent of contribution of the 2GO Travel apprenticeship to students' professional growth in terms of problem-solving and critical thinking abilities. The findings show that the apprenticeship program has a "Very High" ($w\bar{x} = 4.52$) perceived extent of contribution to students' cognitive and analytical skills. The highest mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.57$) is the item "developed my confidence in handling real problems with limited supervision," followed by "trained me to think critically when unexpected problems arise" and "enhanced my decision-making skills under pressure" ($w\bar{x} = 4.54$), and "taught me to create practical solutions in customer-related issues" ($w\bar{x} = 4.49$). Meanwhile, the lowest mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.46$) is the item "improved my ability to analyze and evaluate different work situations." Although identified as the lowest, this rating still falls within the "very high extent, indicating consistently high evaluations across all indicators, with only a small difference of 0.11 between the highest and lowest means. The highest-rated item is "developed my confidence in handling real problems with limited supervision" ($w\bar{x} = 4.57$), which suggests that the apprenticeship fosters independence and self-reliance when confronting workplace challenges. The very high agreement among respondents indicates that the program equips students with the skills to manage problems proactively and confidently. Similarly, "trained me to think critically when unexpected problems arise" and "enhanced my decision-making skills under pressure" received high ratings ($w\bar{x} = 4.54$), reflecting the program's effectiveness in cultivating critical thinking and rapid decision-making in dynamic situations.

According to Yordudom et al. (2025), experiential learning significantly develops Gen Z hospitality students' problem-solving, adaptability, and positive thinking skills, which aligns with the strong impact observed in the 2GO Travel apprenticeship. Besides, the development of critical thinking and reflective decision-making is supported by Alharethi et al. (2025), who found that internship experiences enhance students' work readiness, analytical capabilities, and ability to address real-world challenges effectively. This reinforces the finding that apprenticeships cultivate both confidence and competence in navigating complex professional situations.

The significance of problem-solving and applied decision-making is further supported by Sarkoohi et al. (2024), who demonstrated that structured internship programs improve students' critical thinking disposition, professional confidence, and capacity to manage real challenges under supervision. Although conducted in a nursing context, the study highlights the transferable impact of internship experiences on cognitive skill development across professions. Additionally, the strong effect of reflective and analytical learning during internships is aligned with Nguyen et al. (2021), who reported that work-integrated learning environments expose students to complex situations requiring critical analysis and reflective thinking. This supports the high ratings in involving practical problem-solving and decision-making under pressure.

2.3 Teamwork and Collaboration

Table 2.3 reveals the extent to which the 2GO Travel Apprenticeship contributed to students' professional growth in terms of Teamwork and Collaboration. The findings indicate that the apprenticeship program has a composite mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.55$), reflecting a "Very High" perceived extent of contribution to students' teamwork and collaboration skills. The highest mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.59$) is on the item "helped me learn how to respect and value the contributions of others," followed closely by "developed my cooperation skills in group tasks and projects" ($w\bar{x} = 4.57$), "gave me opportunities to contribute ideas with others, including different opinions and work styles" and "improved my ability to collaborate with people from diverse backgrounds" ($w\bar{x} = 4.54$). Meanwhile, the lowest mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.51$) is on the item "taught me the importance of working well with colleagues." Although identified as the lowest, this rating still falls within the "very high extent", indicating consistently strong evaluations across all indicators, with only a slight difference of 0.08 between the highest and lowest means. The highest-rated item, helped me learn how to respect and value the contributions of others ($w\bar{x} = 4.59$), indicates that the apprenticeship effectively fostered an appreciation for diversity of thought and the importance of mutual respect in professional settings. The very high extent of agreement among respondents reflects the program's success in emphasizing collaborative values, reinforcing teamwork as a core professional skill. Similarly, developed my cooperation skills in group tasks and projects received a high rating ($w\bar{x} = 4.57$), highlighting the practical opportunities the apprenticeship provided for students to engage in joint problem-solving and project-based work, which are essential for real-world workplace readiness.

A structured experiential learning programs, such as the 2GO Travel Apprenticeship, provide a dynamic environment for students to practice teamwork in authentic professional settings. According to Avleeva et al. (2025), internships in hospitality significantly enhance students' soft skills, including communication and collaboration, which aligns with the high ratings observed in this study. Similarly, Pantaruk et al. (2025), emphasized that internships help develop employability through practical experiences that require students to work closely with peers, supporting the observed improvements in cooperation and idea-sharing among respondents. The importance of teamwork in professional skill-building is further reinforced by Navío-Marco et al. (2025),

who found that collaborative learning opportunities, whether online or in-person, strengthen interpersonal and group problem-solving abilities.

Furthermore, Campbell et al. (2025), demonstrated that structured teamwork competency frameworks, like those integrated into internship programs, are effective in helping students cultivate coordination, communication, and collaborative skills. This supports the finding that students in the 2GO Travel Apprenticeship experienced substantial growth in teamwork and collaboration, which are essential for success in real-world professional contexts.

2.4 Career Readiness and Confidence Building

Table 2.4 indicates the extent of contribution of the 2GO Travel apprenticeship to students' professional growth in terms of Career Readiness and Confidence Building. The findings show that the apprenticeship program has a composite mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.56$), indicating a "Very High" perceived extent of contribution to students' career readiness and professional confidence. The highest mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.62$) is on the item "encouraged me to pursue further learning and growth in the industry," followed "by boosted my confidence in handling tasks during my apprenticeship", "given me a clearer idea of my strengths and weaknesses as a future professional" and "inspired me to set career goals and work hard to achieve them" ($w\bar{x} = 4.57$). The lowest mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.49$) is on the item "made me more prepared for future career opportunities." Although this is the lowest among the indicators, it still falls within the "very high extent, showing consistently high evaluations across all items. The findings reveal that the apprenticeship significantly enhances career readiness and professional confidence. This suggests that participating in the 2GO Travel apprenticeship effectively equips students with the skills, self-assurance, and career awareness necessary to succeed in the tourism and hospitality industry.

These findings is the recognized role of internships and work-based learning in fostering employability skills. Cale et al. (2025), found that student internships significantly enhance career readiness skills, enabling students to navigate professional environments effectively. Similarly, Sakinah et al. (2025), reported that internships develop both soft and hard skills, which are crucial for professional competence and confidence in the workplace. The findings also align with Çağlar et al. (2026), who demonstrated that extended internships improve graduate employability and early career outcomes, suggesting that immersive experiences like the 2GO Travel apprenticeship provide tangible benefits for career development. Lian et al. (2024) further support the positive effect of effective internship experiences on employability confidence and vocational identity, which resonates with the high ratings for self-awareness, confidence, and motivation observed in this study.

Relationship between the Extent of the Apprenticeship's Contribution to Students' Learning Experiences and Professional Growth during the 2GO Travel Apprenticeship

Table 3 exposes the relationship between the extent of the 2GO Travel Apprenticeship's contribution to students' learning experiences and professional growth, and the extent to which various factors influence students' development in application of academic knowledge, technical and practical skills, communication and customer service skills, and professional values and work ethics. Using Pearson's Correlation Coefficient, it reveals that all p-values are less than the level of significance (0.05). These figures warrant the rejection of the null hypothesis, indicating that there is a significant relationship between the extent of apprenticeship contributions and students' perceived development across all measured learning and professional growth dimensions.

The results indicate that the application of academic knowledge significantly influences industry exposure and workplace adaptation, problem-solving and critical thinking abilities, teamwork and collaboration, and career readiness and confidence building. This suggests that students' engagement in real-world work scenarios during the apprenticeship plays a crucial role in reinforcing theoretical knowledge, enhancing practical understanding, and fostering confidence in their professional capabilities. This aligns with the findings of Wilopo et al. (2025), who emphasized that structured internship experiences and soft skill competencies significantly improve students' work readiness and professional engagement. Similarly, Kholifah et al. (2025), found that employability skills acquired through internships, including problem-solving and teamwork, substantially contribute to graduate workforce readiness.

Development in technical and practical skills is also found to have a significant relationship with industry exposure, problem-solving, teamwork, and career readiness. This implies that students who actively participate in hands-on activities and task-based learning during apprenticeships are more likely to acquire the practical competencies required for professional success. This is consistent with the study of Kristiawan et al. (2025), which highlighted that work-based learning enhances the link between classroom knowledge and career outcomes, strengthening both skill proficiency and professional adaptability. Additionally, Khuadthong et al. (2025), asserted that work-integrated learning in tourism and hospitality significantly improves communication, teamwork, and problem-solving abilities among students, supporting the observed correlations in this study.

Similarly, enhancement of communication and customer service skills showed significant relationships with all dimensions of professional growth measured, suggesting that exposure to client-facing tasks and collaborative projects during apprenticeships is crucial in cultivating interpersonal competence and service-oriented professionalism. This finding is supported by Khuadthong et al. (2025), who emphasized that work-integrated learning environments foster effective communication and social skills among students.

Strengthening of professional values and work ethics was also significantly correlated with industry exposure, problem-solving, teamwork, and career readiness, implying that apprenticeships provide a meaningful context for students to internalize workplace norms, ethical standards, and professional behaviors. This is consistent with the study of Kristiawan et al. (2025), who highlighted that work-based learning not only develops technical skills but also instills professional ethics and workplace discipline.

Conclusions

The study reveals that the Apprenticeship Adventure with 2GO Travel significantly enhances the learning experiences of Tourism students by improving their ability to apply academic knowledge, develop technical skills, strengthen communication and customer service, and uphold professional values and work ethics. This suggests that hands-on, real-world training plays a vital role in bridging classroom learning with industry practice, enabling students to acquire competencies that are difficult to gain through theory alone. Furthermore, the apprenticeship greatly contributes to students' professional growth by providing industry exposure, fostering problem-solving and critical thinking, enhancing teamwork and collaboration, and building career readiness and confidence. The significant relationship between learning experiences and professional growth indicates that practical training not only develops skills but also shapes students' overall professional development. Overall, these findings emphasize the importance of integrating structured apprenticeship programs into Tourism education to better prepare students for the demands of the tourism and hospitality industry.

Recommendations

The researchers wholeheartedly recommends the following to Students, Higher Educational Institutions, 2GO Travel Management and Future Researchers:

Students

1. Actively engage in apprenticeship opportunities and apply classroom knowledge in real workplace settings.
2. Develop professional skills such as communication, teamwork, adaptability, and time management to enhance workplace performance and career readiness

Higher Educational Institutions

1. Strengthen the integration of classroom learning with real-world application through experiential activities.
2. Require more industry-based apprenticeship experiences in the curriculum.

2GO Travel Management

1. Continuously evaluate and improve the apprenticeship program to ensure it aligns with current industry demands and professional standards.

Future Researchers

1. Conduct similar studies in different institutions or locations to compare results and improve generalizability.
2. Include a larger sample size to obtain more reliable and representative data.
3. Conduct longitudinal studies to assess the long-term impact of tourism apprenticeships on graduate's career success and employability.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study entitled “The Apprenticeship Adventure with 2GO Travel: Its Contribution to the Learning Experiences and Professional Growth of Tourism Students” strictly adhered to ethical principles and guidelines for research involving human participants. All participants were provided with comprehensive and transparent information regarding the study's objectives, methodologies, and their rights to participate voluntarily. Before administering the questionnaire, we ensured that written informed consent was obtained from each respondent, as clearly outlined in the introductory section of the instrument.

The researchers treated all collected responses with the highest level of confidentiality. No personally identifiable information was disclosed or included in the presentation of the findings. Research data were securely stored and accessible only to the research team. Following the completion of the study's presentation and defense, all survey materials were permanently disposed of through shredding, ensuring the utmost data privacy and integrity. Moreover, the institution acknowledged the responsible deployment of artificial intelligence technologies to foster academic innovation, enhance research processes, and streamline administrative functions. AI tools were exclusively utilized for language editing and document formatting purposes. The authors retained full ownership of all intellectual contributions and scholarly inputs.

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